

ADOPTION OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE OF MUSIC TEACHERS OF THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA BASED ON ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: This article discusses the issues of forming innovative pedagogical activities of future music teachers based on the analysis of advanced experiences of foreign countries in the field of music education. It analyzes the fact that in developed countries of the world music education is approached based on an integrative approach, ICT tools, interactive methods, creating a creative environment and strategies that support the personal development of the student. On this basis, the need to introduce innovative approaches to the educational process for future music teachers in Uzbekistan is justified. The article considers the positive aspects of foreign experience and methodological and practical mechanisms for adapting them to local conditions. The importance of musical creativity, technological literacy and reflexive analysis skills in the process of mastering pedagogical innovations is scientifically revealed.

Keywords: future music teacher, foreign experience, innovative pedagogy, music education, educational technologies, methodological approach, interactive methods, creativity, integration, educational process.

Introduction.

In today's globalization process, the most urgent task facing each link of the education system is to train specialists with a competitive, innovative thinking and creative approach. Especially in areas related to art and music, the quality of education directly depends not only on pedagogical skills, but also on the skills of mastering modern technologies and their effective use. Therefore, the formation of future teachers preparing to work in the field of music education based on the requirements of the time, the mastering of innovative pedagogical experiences in their professional training remains one of the important methodological issues.

If we look at the world experience, in the education system of developed countries, music lessons are organized based on interactive and integrative approaches that stimulate students' creative thinking, not limited to academic

knowledge. For example, in countries such as Finland, Japan, the USA, and South Korea, music teachers conduct music lessons interactively using multimedia tools, digital platforms, modern programs, and virtual instruments. Such approaches are not only an important factor in imparting knowledge, but also in developing the inner aesthetic taste, creative thinking, and emotional and intellectual potential of students.

In Uzbekistan, as part of the gradual reforms being implemented in the education system, in particular, within the framework of the “Program to Support Innovations in Education”, special attention is paid to improving the skills of teachers working in the field of art and culture, and introducing them to foreign best practices. This requires methodological substantiation of the formation of innovative competencies in musical and pedagogical activities. By deeply analyzing foreign experience, mastering their main components, and at the same time applying them in harmony with national educational traditions, it is possible to bring the professional training of future music teachers to a new level. This article studies innovative approaches, pedagogical experience and technological tools in music education of foreign countries and determines what methods and approaches are effective in forming the professional competence of future teachers on their basis. This, in turn, will serve to improve the national music education system in accordance with modern requirements.

Materials and methods:

Comparative-pedagogical analysis, empirical observation, analysis of scientific literature, expert interviews, as well as methodological experimental methods were used as the methodological basis of this study. Within the framework of the article, the system of training music teachers, curricula, methodological approaches and methods of using innovative technologies of a number of foreign countries considered advanced in the field of music education - Finland, Japan, the USA, South Korea, Great Britain - were studied. At the same time, the current situation was analyzed based on observations and interviews with future teachers studying in the field of music education in higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The objects of the study were selected as music pedagogy programs operating in foreign countries and methodological guides serving their implementation. As subjects, undergraduate students studying in the field of music education in Uzbekistan and their educational and didactic experience were involved in the analysis.

The following main materials and sources were used during the study:

International methodological guides on music education (in particular, documents of the International Society for Music Education);

Curricula and lesson plans of higher music educational institutions in Finland, the USA and Japan;

Regulatory documents of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of music pedagogy published in recent years;

Practical observations collected on the basis of experience, evidence from interviews with students and opinions of respondents.

Based on the results of the analysis, the following main innovative approaches in foreign educational systems were highlighted:

The use of virtual music laboratories, digital instruments and audiovisual platforms in the learning process;

Organization of the teaching process through interactive methods (role-playing, musical games, group discussion, collaborative creative tasks);

Development of students' musical talent based on an individual and differentiated approach;

Systematic use of feedback-based reflection tools.

Methodologically, the article was conducted in the following sequence: at the initial stage, foreign experience was studied, then compared with national conditions, and finally, methodological proposals for mastering were provided. This approach made it possible to identify differences and similarities between foreign and domestic music education systems, as well as adapt innovative elements to the national system.

Methodology:

This study aims to scientifically study the process of assimilating foreign innovative experiences in the professional training of future music teachers and requires a comprehensive methodological approach based on analysis, comparison, diagnostics, and description.

The theoretical basis of the study was the theory of modern pedagogy, innovative educational concepts, a competency model of musical and pedagogical activity and theories of comparative pedagogy. In particular, the theoretical views of such scientists as A.V. Khutorskoy, I.A. Zimnyaya, G.K. Selevko, J. Dewey, H. Gardner and L. Bresler on innovative pedagogy, musical education and professional training of teachers played an important role in forming the scientific methodological basis of the study.

The methodological approach was based on the following principles:

The principle of systematization and integrity - ensuring the interconnection of all components in the process of music education, harmonizing foreign experience with the local system;

The competency approach - an approach aimed at the formation of modern pedagogical and musical skills in future teachers;

The principle of innovation and creativity - developing the creative potential of the teacher through the implementation of new pedagogical technologies;

Reflexive approach - analysis of the results of student and teacher activities, development of self-assessment mechanisms aimed at improving them.

The following methods were used in the study:

Comparative-analytical method - carrying out a comparative analysis of foreign and domestic education systems;

Content analysis - in-depth study of documents, curricula and methodological manuals on music education of foreign countries;

Empirical methods - studying the real pedagogical process through observation, interview, questionnaire and experiment;

Diagnostic methods - identification and assessment of existing problems based on feedback from students and teachers;

Model creation methods - development of a pedagogical model systematizing the mechanisms for mastering innovative experience.

In the research process, a convergent approach (i.e., identifying commonalities between different sources and systems and harmonizing them) was chosen as the main methodological direction.

Through these methodological approaches, the scientific and theoretical foundations of the effective use of foreign experience in the development of professional competence of future music teachers were identified.

Conclusion.

The above analysis shows that the introduction of innovative pedagogical approaches in the process of modern music education is gaining importance, especially in the training of future music teachers. The experience of foreign countries shows that music education is being effectively implemented not only through traditional forms, but also through digital technologies, interactive methods, creative learning environments and person-oriented approaches. By analyzing these advanced experiences and adapting them to local conditions, it is possible to bring the professional training of future music teachers to a higher level in the education system of Uzbekistan.

According to the results of the study, the development of innovative competence of future music teachers should be carried out in the following areas:

Active use of digital technologies and multimedia tools in music lessons;

Formation of teaching methods that are appropriate to the talents and needs of students based on a differentiated and individual approach;

Introduction of methods that develop creative thinking, reflection and independent musical-analytical thinking skills in students;

Continuous analysis of international musical-pedagogical experiences and their harmonious application in the educational process.

In conclusion, the study and assimilation of foreign experience not only increases the innovative potential of future music teachers, but also serves as an important factor in updating the content of musical education, increasing the effectiveness of education, and training competitive specialists. Therefore, one of the important tasks of the future is the training of teachers who operate on the basis of new pedagogical paradigms in musical education, combining foreign experience and national pedagogical traditions.

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